

NUMERICAL CONSTRUCTION TESTS TO ASSESS THE FEASIBILITY OF PLACEMENT GRIDS FOR CUBIPOD HOMOGENEOUS LOW-CRESTED STRUCTURES

Sergio Muñoz-Palao^{1,*}, Pilar Díaz-Carrasco², Jorge Molines¹, M. Esther Gómez-Martín¹ and Josep R. Medina¹

¹*Universitat Politècnica de València, Institute of Transport and Territory, Camino de Vera s/n, 46022, Valencia, Spain.*

²*University of Cadiz, Algeciras Polytechnic School of Engineering, Avda. Ramón Puyol s/n., 11202, Algeciras (Cádiz), Spain.*

*Corresponding author

E-mail addresses: sermuopa@cam.upv.es (S. Muñoz-Palao), pilar.diaz@gm.uca.es (P. Díaz-Carrasco), jormollo@upv.es (J. Molines), mgomar00@upv.es (M.E. Gómez-Martín), jrmedina@tra.upv.es (J.R. Medina)

ABSTRACT

Placement grid design is a key phase when constructing armor layers in mound breakwaters. Homogeneous Low-Crested Structures (HLCS) are low-crested structures designed as artificial reefs for marine colonization, coral reef regeneration and beach protection. The placement grid affects the construction feasibility, hydraulic stability and wave transmission of HLCS. This study presents a numerical methodology to simulate a realistic placement procedure for armor units during the construction of HLCS. This numerical simulator is based on the open-source physics engine Bullet Physics Engine (BPE), which applies Newton's laws of motion to rigid bodies. From an initial theoretical placement grid for Cubipod HLCS, a series of numerical realistic unit placement tests are carried out to emulate the placement process at prototype scale; placement velocity and spatial deviation of crawler cranes are given parameters associated with each specific project. Considering the placement velocity and spatial deviation during construction, the quality of each specific placement grid is associated with the measured placement errors and the corresponding initial construction deviation to HLCS. This numerical methodology is valuable to understand the influence and the uncertainty of the construction procedure of armor layers in mound breakwaters.

Keywords: Coral reefs; Low-Crested Structures; Placement grid; Placement test; Numerical model; Bullet Physics Engine; Breakwater construction; Cubipod; Armor unit.

1. INTRODUCTION

Low-Crested Structures (LCS) are suitable for shoreline protection and are built to prevent or mitigate erosion (Schoonees et al., 2019). LCS serve as artificial reefs on degraded coral reef areas and fulfil the same function as this natural structure (Airoidi et al., 2005). Additionally, LCS may provide ecosystem services which are beneficial for biodiversity.

Homogeneous Low-Crested Structures (HLCS) are a new typology of Low-Crested Structures (LCS) without a core (Figure 1) built only with large rocks or concrete units (Medina et al., 2019; Odériz et al., 2018). HLCS are designed to be placed on retreating coral reef areas with hard sea beds. In addition, HLCS can foster marine fauna whilst protecting the shoreline; the high porosity of HLCS favors coral reef colonization and restoration of marine habitats (Sherrard et al., 2016). The proposed design of HLCS as coastal protection structures matches green infrastructure requirements: a solution that also meets social, economic and environmental needs (Silva et al., 2017). HLCS present advantages compared to traditional LCS as discussed by Medina et al. (2022): large rocks are not necessary; they are relatively easily repaired

51 and dismantled; different light exposures are possible within the highly porous structure; other advantages
52 include coralline colonization, promotion of marine life, ecosystem regeneration, and sustainable attraction
53 of fishes and tourists.

54

55 *Figure 1. Typical cross-section for: (a) conventional Low-Crested Structures (LCS) and (b) Homogeneous Low-Crested*
56 *Structures (HLCS).*

57 HLCS are multi-layered structures, and their placement grid affects porosity and layer thickness coefficients
58 (Molines et al., 2021). For the same number of layers, a grid with higher porosity results in a lower structure
59 height and crest freeboard. Since wave transmission of HLCS mainly depends on the crest freeboard, the
60 placement grid design is key to guarantee the structure functionality (Medina et al., 2020). Furthermore,
61 the placement procedure may lead to initial deviations and loss of units during construction which may also
62 affect the hydraulic stability during service time. Cubipods (and other armor units) are placed following X-
63 Y placement grid coordinates using a GPS differential system (Medina & Gómez-Martín, 2016). The GPS
64 precision error and other errors during the placement process may result in an initial construction deviation
65 during the construction of HLCS. The X-Y positioning errors of lower layers in HLCS induce errors in
66 upper layers; if the X-Y positioning error corresponding to a given placement grid is too large, the
67 construction of HLCS is considered unfeasible because very large initial deviations are generated during
68 construction.

69 Realistic small-scale physical placement tests have been used to check the feasibility of given placement
70 grids. These physical tests may provide valuable information regarding the construction process, although
71 they are time-consuming and require specific equipment and trained small-scale crane operators (Pardo et
72 al., 2014). On the other hand, numerical models can be used to analyze the suitability of placement grids
73 for HLCS. Numerical models may be classified in two main groups: (1) models based on finite and discrete
74 element methods (FEMDEM) and (2) physics engines that are commonly used for game development and
75 animation. The FEMDEM models are complex with a high computational cost; they are able to compute
76 interaction, stress and deformation of armor units. Physics engines are much simpler and computationally
77 time-efficient; they are based on rigid body physics and laws of classical mechanics

78 Latham et al. (2008) studied the interaction of several armor unit geometries with FEMDEM models and
79 concluded that results obtained including forces and stresses were similar to those measured in experimental
80 pull-out tests. Later, Latham et al. (2013) and Anastasaki et al. (2015) examined placement grids of Core-
81 Loc armors with Y3D-R, a FEMDEM method, developed by Xiang et al. (2009). Numerical placement
82 tests following a placement grid helped to understand placement orientation and armor packing, although
83 no spatial deviation was considered. A placement procedure was defined in a cycle. The lowering velocity
84 was controlled and reduced progressively when armor units were in contact. The high computational cost is
85 the main drawback when using FEMDEM modelling with multi-body particle interaction to simulate armor
86 placement.

87 Cooper et al. (2008, 2010) used a game engine (PhysX Physics Engine) to study the armor placement of
88 Dolos and Antifer units and tested the interaction of these armor units with the rock underlayer, while
89 Greben et al. (2010) studied interaction under oscillatory forces of Antifer armored mound breakwaters.
90 However, these numerical results were not calibrated or validated with physical results.

91 Bullet Physics Engine (BPE) is an open-source, robust and low time-consuming physics engine (Coumans,
92 2015). It is based on Newton's laws of motion and rigid body physics; BPE is adequate for the realistic
93 simulation of the motion of multiple rigid bodies (Boeing & Bräunl, 2007; Erez et al., 2015). Consequently,
94 BPE is convenient to simulate the placement of massive armor units such as Cubipod units in HLCS.
95 Numerical placement tests using BPE were validated with small-scale physical tests of Cubipod HLCS to
96 measure layer coefficients (Centi, 2020; De Keyser & Jacobs, 2020; Molines et al., 2021). However, in

97 Molines et al. (2021), all armor units were placed simultaneously without controlling their placement
98 velocity. In this study, the armor units are placed one by one at a controlled placement velocity.

99 The goal of this study is to provide a numerical methodology with the physics engine BPE for the realistic
100 construction of HLCS, specifically 3-layer Cubipod HLCS. A series of numerical placement tests using
101 equilateral triangular grids with different nominal porosities were carried out to analyze the construction
102 feasibility depending on the placement conditions of the simulated crawler crane: placement velocity and
103 placement deviation due to adverse wave conditions or GPS error positioning. The numerical simulations
104 helped to understand the uncertainty of the construction and the initial deviation obtained based on
105 positioning errors.

106 This paper is structured as follows: firstly, a literature review is given in Section 2; Section 3 describes the
107 methodology for the numerical placement of Cubipod units; Section 4 describes the numerical construction
108 tests carried out in this study. Numerical test results are given in Section 5, and conclusions are offered later
109 in Section 6.

110 2. PLACEMENT GRIDS FOR CUBIPOD HLCS

111 A placement grid is a scheme that indicates the placement position of armor units in an armor layer.
112 Placement grids follow geometrical patterns described by geometrical characteristics and parameters. For
113 Cubipod HLCS, the placement grid identifies the $\{X,Y\}$ horizontal position of the center of mass for each
114 unit to be placed; the parameters (a and b) characterize the separation between rows of Cubipod units in
115 the perpendicular to the trunk ($a \cdot D_n$) and the separation among units parallel to the trunk ($b \cdot D_n$), in which
116 D_n is the nominal diameter of the concrete unit.

117 Rectangular Placement Grids (RPG) and Triangular Placement Grids (TPG) were studied by (Odériz et al.
118 (2018), and after analyzing results from 2D small-scale physical tests on the wave flume, TPG were found
119 to be better than RPG from the hydraulic stability point of view. These physical models were constructed
120 by hand following the corresponding placement grids. The best results were observed for TPG with
121 parameters $a=1.27$ and $b=1.58$ (Medina et al., 2019); Figure 2 shows an example of RPG and TPG grids
122 studied for HLCS.

123
124 Figure 2. HLCS placement grids: (a) Rectangular Placement Grid (RPG) and (b) Triangular Placement Grid (TPG).

125 The design of placement grids is related to the observed hydraulic performance of HLCS in small-scale
126 physical testing; hydraulic stability and wave transmission are key structural responses to be taken into
127 consideration (Medina et al., 2019; Odériz et al., 2018). Wave transmission is mainly related to the crest
128 freeboard. Contrary to conventional LCS, the height of HLCS depends on the number of layers, the nominal
129 porosity of the placement grid and the Cubipod size. For this reason, Medina et al. (2020) noted the
130 importance of establishing a clear criterion to measure layer coefficients and to properly estimate structure
131 height and crest freeboard. Consequently, De Keyser & Jacobs (2020) carried out small-scale physical tests
132 to estimate the layer coefficients of different RPG and TPG for Cubipod HLCS, and their corresponding
133 BPE numerical tests were conducted by Centi (2020) and Molines et al. (2021). The good agreement
134 between physical and numerical tests highlighted the utility of BPE to simulate placement procedures
135 although Molines et al. (2021) did not place armor units one by one and at a controlled placement velocity.

136 HLCS are multi-layer structures which require a placement grid for each layer. Similar placement grids
137 must be used in each layer for the same HLCS, and they must be aligned with each other to place the units
138 of upper layers between four (RPG) or three (TPG) units of the lower layer. Figure 3 shows placement grids
139 for 2-layer and 3-layer Cubipod HLCS for both RPG and TPG.

140

141 *Figure 3. Multi-layer placement grids: (a) 2-layer RPG, (b) 3-layer-RPG, (c) 2-layer TPG and (d) 3-layer TPG.*

142 **2.1. Nominal and void porosity**

143 Void porosity (p_v) is defined as the ratio of volume of voids to the total volume of a granular system.
 144 Although being intuitive and a decisive factor for the hydraulic stability, void porosity is hard to measure
 145 in armor layers of mound breakwaters (Medina et al., 2011). Instead of using the void porosity as a
 146 placement armor descriptor, engineering manuals often refers a nominal porosity associated with a specific
 147 layer coefficient (USACE, 1984; CIRIA, CUR, CETMEF, 2007).

148 Placement density or dimensionless packing density are the key parameters to characterize the placement
 149 process (concrete consumption, etc.); these are related to both nominal porosity and layer coefficient. The
 150 placement density (φ), described in the SPM (1984), can be defined as a function of the parameters of the
 151 placement grid:

$$\varphi = n \cdot k_A \cdot \frac{1 - p_n}{D_n^2} = \frac{1}{a \cdot b \cdot D_n^2} \quad (1)$$

152 where n is the number of layers, k_A is the layer coefficient, p_n is the nominal porosity, D_n is the nominal
 153 diameter and $\{a, b\}$ are the parameters of the placement grid (see Figure 2).

154 For HLCS, different layer coefficients k_A are measured for each layer, as indicated by De Keyser & Jacobs
 155 (2020). Since k_A may vary, every layer has a different void porosity p_v . The void porosity p_v equals the
 156 nominal porosity p_n only if $k_A=1.00$. Therefore, each layer is defined by its nominal porosity p_n assuming a
 157 layer coefficient $k_A=1.00$. Thus, the nominal porosity p_n used to describe all placement grids is given by

$$p_n = 1 - \frac{1}{a \cdot b} \quad (2)$$

158 Odériz et al. (2018) selected the TPG with $a=1.27$ and $b=1.58$ as the best grid for Cupidod HLCS; Medina
 159 et al. (2020) highlighted that this placement grid is similar to an equilateral triangular grid ($a = b \cdot \sqrt{3}/2$).
 160 with a nominal porosity $p_n=0.50$. In this study, the one-parameter equilateral TPG is studied ($0.50 \leq p_n \leq 0.55$)
 161 for 3-layer Cupidod HLCS. Table 1 shows the nominal porosities related to the parameters of the placement
 162 grids used in this study. A grid with a nominal porosity lower than $p_n=0.50$ or higher than $p_n=0.55$ may be

163 unfeasible in practice. This range of appropriate porosities is based on tests performed by De Keyser &
164 Jacobs (2020).

165 *Table 1. Nominal porosity and geometric grid parameters considered in this study.*

Nominal porosity	p_n	0.500	0.525	0.550
Perpendicular to the trunk direction	a	1.32	1.35	1.39
Paralell to the trunk direction	b	1.52	1.56	1.60

166

167 **2.2. Initial triangular placement grids (TPG0)**

168 As described in the previous sections, placement grids are necessary to build prototypes as well as small-
169 scale physical models. Differences between physical models and prototypes are likely to occur depending
170 on the placement grid and the construction conditions. To this end, feasible placement grids must consider
171 the construction procedure (placement velocity and positioning error) in addition to the placement order.

172 In this study, initial theoretical triangular placement grids (TPG0) are defined by several one-parameter
173 equilateral TPG, as shown in Figure 2 and Table 1. Equilateral triangles are oriented with one in the seaward
174 direction and two in the leeward direction (triangles are pointing to incoming waves) according to Odériz
175 et al. (2018). The placement grids of the upper layers are aligned one to another over the barycenter of the
176 triangles of the lower layer (see Figure 3 and Figure 4). HLCS are usually constructed as detached LCS:
177 parallel to the shoreline and bathymetric contours.

178 The three TPG corresponding to TPG0 depend on the layer level ($k=1, 2$ and 3), and describe columns ($i=1,$
179 $2,$ etc.) perpendicular to the trunk, and rows ($j=1, 2,$ etc.) parallel to the trunk. Indexes i, j and k are used in
180 the placement grid to indicate number of column, number of row and layer level, respectively. With this
181 scheme, the number of columns is related to the length of the structure, parallel to the shoreline, while the
182 number of rows is related to the width of the structure. The number of layers is related to the breakwater
183 height and crest freeboard.

184 Cubipods of each HLCS model were placed one by one with a constant placement velocity and, Cubipods
185 were placed following a placement order: (1) the lower layer is completed before placing any unit
186 corresponding to an upper layer, (2) each column is completed before initiating the placement of the
187 following column, and (3) units are placed starting with the deepest point of each column. Therefore, the
188 units of the lowest row are placed first in each column. The placement procedure for the TPG0 is also
189 described in Figure 4.

190
191

Figure 4. Initial triangular placement grids (TPG0) for multi-layer HLCS.

192 3. METHODOLOGY FOR NUMERICAL PLACEMENT OF CUBIPOD ARMOR UNITS

193 Based on realistic construction requirements, a numerical placement procedure is described in this section.
194 Firstly, the BPE numerical model is described. Secondly, BPE parameters are calibrated to simulate
195 placement velocities similar to the real velocities of crawler cranes. Finally, a spatial deviation is used
196 to simulate Gaussian X-Y horizontal positioning errors when placing Cubipod units with crawler cranes; this
197 error in the unit positioning may be caused by wind, currents and wave conditions as well as GPS precision
198 errors.

199 3.1. Bullet Physics Engine (BPE)

200 BPE is a physics engine, presented by Coumans (2015); it can simulate the physical response of objects
201 under the action of external forces, and it is incorporated in the open-software (Blender, 2021). This engine
202 is based on Newton's laws of motion and uses Euler's Method to estimate the motion properties of all
203 objects during the simulation. The details of the BPE mathematical model used in this study are given by
204 Molines et al. (2021). In addition, more information about physics engines can be found in Millington
205 (2007).

206 For every object in the BPE simulations, variations in linear and angular velocities are described by

$$\dot{p}_{i+1} = \dot{p}_i - \dot{p}_i \cdot ld + \ddot{p}_i \cdot \Delta t \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{\theta}_{i+1} = \dot{\theta}_i - \dot{\theta}_i \cdot ad + \ddot{\theta}_i \cdot \Delta t \quad (4)$$

207 where \dot{p}_i and \dot{p}_{i+1} are the linear velocities for time steps i and $i+1$, acceleration \ddot{p}_i is considered at time step
208 i , and Δt is the time interval of the simulation. This is the same for $\dot{\theta}_{i+1}$, $\dot{\theta}_i$ and $\ddot{\theta}_i$ which are final angular
209 velocity, initial angular velocity and initial angular acceleration, respectively. Linear damping (ld) and
210 angular damping (ad) are parameters used to slow the physical response of any moving object.

211 BPE simulations require a series of parameters to provide a realistic response using rigid bodies:

- 212 • Friction (μ) is the ratio between normal and tangential forces in a collision ($0 \leq \mu \leq 1$).
- 213 • Bounciness (e) is the ratio between final and initial velocity after a collision ($0 \leq e \leq 1$). It describes
214 the proportion of energy lost during a collision ($e=0$, inelastic collision; $e=1$, elastic collision) and
215 it is related to the restitution coefficient which is a material property.
- 216 • Linear damping (ld) is a numerical parameter ($0 \leq ld \leq 1$) to reduce the linear velocity over time.
- 217 • Angular damping (ad) is a numerical parameter ($0 \leq ad \leq 1$) to reduce the angular velocity over time.

218 • Collision Margin (CM) is the threshold ($0.001 \leq CM[m] \leq 1$) in which collisions between rigid
 219 bodies are considered. It is the margin of error needed for BPE to detect contact between units in
 220 a simulation.

221 One of the limitations of the BPE is that objects cannot be simulated to be placed at any desired velocity;
 222 they fall freely instead. Because of this, Molines et al. (2021) proposed a small enough Falling Distance
 223 (FD) so that placement velocity at the instant of the collision was small but it was also unknown. The FD
 224 was defined as the distance between the unit and the imaginary surface formed by the envelope of the
 225 previous layer level or the bottom surface (see Figure 6).

226 Molines et al. (2021) calibrated the BPE to measure layer coefficients of Cubipod HLCS. A sensitivity
 227 analysis was carried out to compare numerical and small-scale physical results. The parameters that showed
 228 the best agreement between estimated and measured layer thickness were $D_n=1.07m$, $\mu=0.6$, $e=0$,
 229 $FD=0.25 \cdot D_n$, $ld=0$, $ad=0$, and $CM=0.008 \cdot D_n$; the tested range of parameters was $0.53 \leq D_n[m] \leq 2.14$, $0.6 \leq$
 230 $\mu \leq 0.8$, $0 \leq e \leq 1$, $0.10 \cdot D_n \leq FD \leq 0.40 \cdot D_n$, $0 \leq ld \leq 1$, $0 \leq ad \leq 1$, and $0.008 \cdot D_n \leq CM \leq 0.012 \cdot D_n$.

231 3.2. Numerical armor unit placement

232 A placement velocity similar to actual crawler crane operations is one of the key conditions for a realistic
 233 numerical placement. From the BPE, parameters ld and ad affect changes in the velocity and rotation over
 234 time in the simulation, as described in Eqs. (3) and (4). Thus, a series of numerical drop tests was conducted
 235 in order to find a realistic placement velocity. In these preliminary simulations, the vertical position is
 236 obtained for every time step, and the velocity is then calculated from the vertical position over time.

237 Figure 5 shows the placement velocity over time considering different values of linear damping ($0 \leq ld < 1$).

238 After a few seconds, a constant fall velocity is the result in time of setting a given linear damping ($0 \leq ld < 1$);
 239 the higher the linear damping, the lower the falling velocity. The angular damping does not affect the fall
 240 velocity. The Falling Distance (FD) used by Molines et al. (2021) is not required since a controlled
 241 placement velocity is obtained eventually (see

242 Figure 5). Numerical precision prevents placement velocities lower than $v=0.64$ m/s. This placement
 243 velocity corresponds to a linear damping value $ld=1-10^{-7}$. Moreover, the placement velocity obtained by
 244 modifying ld in Figure 5 is independent from the Cubipod size; Eqs. **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen**
 245 **de la referencia.** and **¡Error! No se encuentra el origen de la referencia.** are not influenced by the size,
 246 shape or weight of the object in the numerical model (Millington, 2007; Coumans, 2015). These preliminary
 247 simulations were performed for the three armor unit sizes studied by Molines et al. (2021): $D_n[m]=\{0.53,$
 248 $1.07, 2.14\}$.

249

250 Figure 5. Placement velocity over time for different linear damping values (ld).

251 3.3. Numerical and prototype placement velocity

252 Placement velocities higher than $v=1$ m/s can be numerically simulated by selecting the appropriate linear
 253 damping value $ld < 1-10^{-7}$ (see

254 Figure 5). However, prototype placement vertical velocities may be lower than $v=1$ m/s, as indicated in the
 255 Cubipod Manual (Medina & Gómez-Martín, 2016) with placement cycles of 6 to 8 min. To properly
 256 simulate low prototype placement velocities, an appropriate geometric scale between the prototype and the
 257 numerical model must be used. The criterion to calculate the adequate geometric scale is to maintain a
 258 constant ratio between potential and kinetic energy in model and prototype, a Froude similarity. For model
 259 and prototype, the ratio between kinetic energy and potential energy is given by

$$kp = \frac{E_{kinetic}}{E_{potential}} = \frac{mv^2/2}{mgD_n} = \frac{v^2}{2gD_n} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{v_p^2}{2gD_{n,p}} = \frac{v_n^2}{2gD_{n,n}} \quad (6)$$

260 where kp is the kinetic-to-potential energy ratio, v is the placement velocity (v_p prototype and v_n numerical),
 261 D_n is the nominal diameter of the Cubipod ($D_{n,p}$ prototype and $D_{n,n}$ numerical) and g is the gravity
 262 acceleration. A lower kp ratio indirectly translates into a lower placement velocity compared to armor unit
 263 size; a larger-than-prototype Cubipod size may be required for the numerical model to maintain the same
 264 kinetic-to-potential energy ratio in the prototype and numerical model.

265 In addition, different kp ratios ($0.005 \leq kp \leq 0.080$) are used to represent feasible placement velocities at
 266 prototype-scale. This range covers the damping of energy that occurs in realistic placement scenarios; that
 267 is, the lower is the kp , the more damping and lesser energy goes into moving the unit or vice versa. These
 268 velocities are idealized to isolate different placement productivity rates. The prototype-scale size selected
 269 is $D_{n,p}[\text{m}]=1.07$. Thus, the nominal diameter of the numerical model ($D_{n,n}$) can be calculated using Eq. (6)
 270 for any given prototype crane operation characteristics $\{v_p, D_{n,p}\}$ once a numerical placement velocity (v_n)
 271 is defined. In this study, a fixed linear damping value $ld=0.9999$ is selected that corresponds to a numerical
 272 placement velocity $v_n=1.09$ m/s, (see

273 Figure 5), which is similar to the placement cycles stated in the Cubipod Manual (Medina & Gómez-Martín,
 274 2016).

275 To sum up, each pair of numerical placement velocity and armor unit size $\{v_n, D_{n,n}\}$ in Eq. (6) corresponds
 276 to a prototype pair $\{v_p, D_{n,p}\}$. As an example, Table 2 shows the relationship between prototype and
 277 numerical scales for a selected kinetic-to-potential energy ratio (kp).

278 *Table 2. Placement velocities and Cubipod sizes for the selected kinetic-to-potential energy ratios (kp) between*
 279 *prototype and numerical scale ($D_{n,p}=1.07$ m and $v_n=1.09$ m/s).*

kp [-]	Prototype scale		Numerical scale	
	v_p [m/s]	$D_{n,p}$ [m]	v_n [m/s]	$D_{n,n}$ [m]
0.005	0.32	1.07	1.09	12.11
0.010	0.46	1.07	1.09	6.06
0.020	0.65	1.07	1.09	3.03
0.040	0.92	1.07	1.09	1.51
0.080	1.30	1.07	1.09	0.76

280 3.4. Numerical crane positioning error

281 The theoretical $\{X,Y\}$ coordinates are different from the actual $\{X,Y\}$ placement coordinates due to errors
 282 induced by wind, currents and wave conditions, as well as differential GPS errors corresponding to the
 283 crawler crane (see Medina and Gómez-Martín, 2016). In the numerical model, a dimensionless crane spatial
 284 deviation (Δ/D_n) is considered to modify slightly and randomly the theoretical placement position on the
 285 placement grid. The spatial deviation proposed in this study is a theoretical approach to consider all
 286 placement errors. The expected placement error follows a Gaussian distribution, $\gamma \sim N(0, \Delta/D_n)$, in which
 287 Δ/D_n is the variance in the error. If currents are added, the mean of the gaussian distribution can be modified.
 288 The coordinates for each grid point after considering random GPS placement errors are given by

$$X_1 = X_0 + \gamma \cdot D_n \quad (7)$$

$$Y_1 = Y_0 + \gamma \cdot D_n \quad (8)$$

289 where, $\gamma \sim N(0, \Delta/D_n)$ is the dimensionless placement error corresponding to a given dimensionless crane
 290 spatial deviation Δ/D_n , X_0 and Y_0 are the theoretical grid coordinates from the TPG0 (see Figure 4) and X_1
 291 and Y_1 are the placement grid coordinates considering the placement errors. The tested crane spatial
 292 deviation values considered for this study are in the range $0.00 \leq \Delta/D_n \leq 0.20$.

293 4. NUMERICAL CONSTRUCTION TESTS

294 Numerical construction tests of Cubipod HLCS were conducted using the open-software Blender (2021)
 295 that includes the BPE numerical model described in Section 3.1. Firstly, a numerical placement procedure
 296 is defined; secondly, the parameters of the BPE numerical model are selected, and finally, a test matrix is
 297 designed to carry out the numerical experiments.

298 In this study, 3-layer Cubipod HLCS are analyzed. HLCS models have 12, 11 and 10 columns and 7, 6 and
 299 5 rows for the first, second and third layer, respectively. HLCS models are constructed over a surface with
 300 a constant slope (m) to mimic a uniform sea bottom.

301 4.1. Numerical placement procedure

302 Cubipod units are placed following the construction order starting with the TPG0 (see Figure 4). The
 303 numerical placement procedure used Eq. (6), and Eqs. (7) and (8) to consider the given prototype
 304 construction conditions kp and Δ/D_n . The kinetic-to-potential energy ratio (kp) affects $D_{n,n}$ (6) while the
 305 crane positioning error depends on the dimensionless crane spatial deviation (Δ/D_n) described in Eqs. (7)
 306 and (8).

307 The placement procedure of a single armor unit is defined by the following cycle, an example is given in
 308 Figure 6.:

- 309 1) The Cubipod unit is set with their corresponding linear damping (ld) and numerical-scale size
 310 ($D_{n,n}$) for the selected kinetic-to-potential ratio (kp) and a given prototype-scale placement velocity
 311 and size $\{v_p, D_{n,p}\}$,
- 312 2) The unit is randomly oriented and placed over its vertical projection at their corresponding grid
 313 coordinates $\{X, Y\}$ considering a crane spatial deviation (Δ/D_n),
- 314 3) The unit is placed,
- 315 4) The placement procedure cycle ends once it consumes three times the time needed to be lowered
 316 from approximately $FD=1.5 \cdot D_{n,n}$. This FD was found to be adequate for all cases to avoid
 317 numerical inconsistency (see Figure 6).

318
 319 *Figure 6. Numerical placement procedure of a Cubipod unit of the 3rd-layer, as defined in Section 4.1. Falling Distance*
 320 *$FD=1.5 \cdot D_{n,n}$ (indicated in yellow).*

321 4.2. BPE parameters for simulations

322 The selected BPE parameters for the numerical experiments are given in Table 3. Some of the parameters
 323 are selected considering the results of the tests conducted by Molines et al. (2021): $\mu=0.6$, $e=0$, $ad=0$ and
 324 $CM=0.008 \cdot D_{n,n}$. Realistic construction requires using the following parameters: $FD=1.5 \cdot D_{n,n}$ and $ld=0.9999$
 325 ($v_n=1.09$ m/s). The nominal diameter of the Cubipod units in the numerical model ($D_{n,n}$) depends on ld and
 326 prototype $\{v_p, D_{n,p}\}$ according to Eq. (6). Thus, $D_{n,n}$ is set according to prototype placement conditions

327 (0.32 ≤ v_p [m/s] ≤ 1.30 and $D_{n,p}$ [m] = 1.07), as shown in Table 2. Mass density of Cubipod units is set to 2,300
 328 kg/m³.

329 Table 3. BPE parameters used for numerical simulations.

Parameter name	Symbol	Values
Nominal diameter	$D_{n,n}$ [m]	{12.11, 6.06, 3.03, 1.51, 0.76}
Falling Distance	FD	$1.5 \cdot D_{n,n}$
Friction	μ	0.6
Bounciness	e	0
Linear damping	ld	0.9999
Angular damping	ad	0
Collision Margin	CM	$0.008 \cdot D_{n,n}$

330

331 4.3. Test Matrix design for realistic construction tests

332 The text matrix of this study is described by Table 4. The numerical simulations were carried out with
 333 different values of nominal porosity (p_n), bottom slope (m), dimensionless kinetic-to-potential energy ratio
 334 (kp/D_n) and dimensionless crane spatial deviation (Δ/D_n). Firstly, numerical simulation tests were
 335 conducted considering $\Delta/D_n=0$ (no crane positioning error) following the placement grid TPG0 (Figure 4)
 336 and the numerical placement procedure defined in Section 4.1. Secondly, four crane positioning error were
 337 considered ($\Delta/D_n>0$). The range of parameters tested is $0.500 \leq p_n \leq 0.550$, $0.00 \leq m \leq 0.06$, $0.005 \leq kp \leq 0.08$ and
 338 $0.00 \leq \Delta/D_n \leq 0.20$ (see Table 4). A total of 3,000 numerical tests was carried out; 300 different configurations
 339 were considered, and 10 tests were completed for each configuration to take into account the randomness
 340 of the placement process (random unit orientation, etc.).

341 Table 4. Test matrix used for this study.

Parameter name	Symbol	Values
Nominal porosity	p_n	{0.500, 0.525, 0.550}
Bottom slope	m	{0.00, 0.02, 0.04, 0.06}
Kinetic-to-potential energy ratio	kp	{0.005, 0.010, 0.020, 0.040, 0.080}
Dimensionless crane spatial deviation	Δ/D_n	{0, 0.050, 0.100, 0.150, 0.200}

342

343 5. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

344 This section explains the results from numerical simulations using the initial placement grid (TPG0) with
 345 different porosities (p_n), bottom slopes (m) and prototype handling conditions (kp and Δ/D_n).

346 5.1. Positioning errors related to TPG0

347 Results from numerical placement tests were analyzed for the cases described in Table 4. Horizontal {X,Y}
 348 coordinates were measured for every Cubipod unit (center of mass) in each layer. Projected positioning
 349 errors, (ε_x and ε_y), were the deviation between the original {X,Y} coordinates of the grid TPG0 and the
 350 final {X,Y} ones.

351 The numerical experiments resulted in different positioning errors (ε_x and ε_y) depending on the placement
 352 conditions (bottom slope, vertical velocity, etc.). ε_x and ε_y were analyzed by sorting them according to the
 353 nominal porosity (p_n), slope (m) and placement conditions (kp and Δ/D_n). ε_x and ε_y were found to follow a
 354 Gaussian distribution: $\varepsilon_x \sim N(\mu_{\varepsilon_x}, \sigma_{\varepsilon_x}^2)$ and $\varepsilon_y \sim N(\mu_{\varepsilon_y}, \sigma_{\varepsilon_y}^2)$. This was proven with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov
 355 goodness-of-fit test, in which more than 95% of numerical experimental results were Gaussian distributed.

356 Figure 7 shows the mean values of the projected positioning errors (μ_{ε_x} and μ_{ε_y}) corresponding to the first
 357 layer of Cubipod units placed on a sea bottom with constant slope without considering any positioning error
 358 ($\Delta/D_n=0$). Crane spatial deviation was null ($\Delta/D_n=0$) in simulations but positioning errors ε_x and ε_y were
 359 not.

360 Along the X-axis, parallel to the bathymetric lines, the mean value of the X-positioning error (μ_{ε_x}) is positive
 361 for all columns except the first one; in this case $\mu_{\varepsilon_x} \approx 0$. The final positioning of units is slightly expanded

362 when compared to the original grid TPG0 (see Figure 7a); this expansion is higher if the placement velocity
 363 (v_n is related to kp) is higher, and lower if the nominal porosity (p_n) is higher.

364 On the Y-axis, perpendicular to the bathymetric lines, the mean value of the Y-positioning error (μ_{ey})
 365 depends mainly on the bottom slope (m). The mean positioning error for every row and column tends to be
 366 similar depending only on m (see Figure 7b); the higher the bottom slope (m), the higher the positioning
 367 error. Gravity tends to displace the units downwards.

368

369 *Figure 7. Mean values of the projected positioning errors for $\Delta/D_n=0$, as a function of the nominal porosity (p_n), bottom*
 370 *slope (m) and kinetic-to-potential energy ratio (kp): (a) X-axis and (b) Y-axis.*

371 The scatter of ϵ_x and ϵ_y is mainly driven by the dimensionless crane spatial deviation parameter (Δ/D_n).
 372 Higher Δ/D_n resulted in higher values for positioning errors ϵ_x and ϵ_y . For cases given in Table 4, the
 373 following trends were observed: $\sigma_{\epsilon_x}^2 \approx \sigma_{\epsilon_y}^2 \approx 0.125$ for $\Delta/D_n \leq 0.05$ and $\sigma_{\epsilon_x}^2 \approx \sigma_{\epsilon_y}^2 \approx 0.180$ for $\Delta/D_n \geq 0.10$.

374 A scheme of the positioning error trend is given in Figure 8. It shows a displaced and expanded average
 375 grid (in red) when the original grid TPG0 is constructed (in black). The expansion of the placement grid in
 376 the bottom layer affects the positioning error of grids in upper layers. Wider grids have lower layer
 377 coefficients (De Keyser & Jacobs, 2020; Molines et al., 2021); thus, the final crest freeboard will be slightly
 378 different from that expected when using TPG0.

379

380 *Figure 8. Expanded and displaced average grid (in red) of the first layer following the original grid TPG0 (in black).*

381 **5.2. Positioning errors as performance indicators**

382 From the trend observed when using a TPG0 (see Figure 8), the placement grid above the first layer will
 383 not be perfectly aligned to the bottom grid; thus, the positioning errors in the bottom layer influence the
 384 upper layers, and units placed in upper layers are less likely to find a correct resting positions. To this end,
 385 measuring positioning errors can be useful to assess the quality of the construction procedure.

386 The projected positioning errors (ϵ_x and ϵ_y) tend to follow a Gaussian distribution as stated in Section 5.1.
 387 Therefore, positioning errors $\epsilon=(\epsilon_x^2+\epsilon_y^2)^{0.5}$ are approximately Rayleigh distributed. To this end, the
 388 dimensionless root mean squared error of positioning errors (ϵ_{rms}/D_n) is used in this study as a placement
 389 performance indicator. As expected, results show larger ϵ_{rms}/D_n for higher kinetic-to-potential energy ratio
 390 (kp) and dimensionless crane spatial deviation (Δ/D_n), (Figure 9).

391

392 *Figure 9. ϵ_{rms}/D_n corresponding to porosity $p_n=0.500$ related to (a) $m=0.00$ and (b) $m=0.06$ for different combinations*
 393 *of kinetic-to-potential energy ratio (kp) and dimensionless crane spatial deviation (Δ/D_n).*

394 Eq. (9) is fitted to results observed from numerical simulations of the cases described in Table 4. This can
 395 be used to estimate ϵ_{rms} as a function of p_n , m , kp , and Δ/D_n :

$$\epsilon_{rms}/D_n = \begin{cases} 0.139 + m + (6.961 - 10.915 \cdot p_n) \cdot kp + (0.744 - 0.747 \cdot p_n) \cdot \Delta/D_n & \text{if } \Delta/D_n \leq 0.05 \\ 0.059 + m + (9.206 - 15.178 \cdot p_n) \cdot kp + (2.739 - 2.452 \cdot p_n) \cdot \Delta/D_n & \text{if } 0.10 \leq \Delta/D_n \leq 0.20 \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

396 where p_n is the nominal porosity, m is the bottom slope, kp is the kinetic-to-potential energy ratio and Δ/D_n
 397 is the dimensionless crane spatial deviation. Eq. (9) is valid in the ranges $0.500 \leq p_n \leq 0.550$, $0 \leq m \leq 0.06$ and
 398 $0.005 \leq kp \leq 0.08$.

399

400 *Figure 10. TPG0: Comparison between observed and estimated ϵ_{rms}/D_n using Eq. (9).*

401 **5.3. Initial construction deviations corresponding to TPG0**

402 Although ϵ_{rms} may be used as a performance estimator in the placement simulations, a quantitative indicator
 403 is more convenient for understanding the quality of the construction procedure. It is defined as the
 404 percentage of significant deviations, $\epsilon/D_n \geq 1$, from the theoretical placement grid. In this study, $N\%$
 405 is calculated for each numerical simulation and is given by

$$N\% = \frac{N_o}{N_{total}} \quad (10)$$

406 where N_o is the number of units significantly deviated, $\epsilon/D_n \geq 1$, and N_{tot} is the total number of armor units
 407 in the HLCS, $N_{tot} = 266$ for this study. $N\%$ is the percentage of units displaced. The correlation coefficient
 408 between observed ϵ_{rms}/D_n and $N\%$ indicators is equal to $r=0.862$, as shown in Figure 11.

409

410 *Figure 11. Representation of two measured indicators $\{\epsilon_{rms}/D_n, N\%\}$ in numerical construction simulations and the*
 411 *Start of Significant Deviations threshold (red).*

412 ϵ_{rms}/D_n is a numerical estimator while $N\%$ is a physical indicator, both measuring the quality of the
 413 placement procedure. For instance, Figure 12 shows how ϵ_{rms}/D_n and $N\%$ increase gradually for three
 414 different placement conditions (kp and Δ/D_n) when the construction of a Cubipod HLCS is simulated with
 415 a porosity $p_n=0.500$, and a bottom slope $m=0.04$. As a consequence, it is convenient in practice to find
 416 which handling conditions (kp and Δ/D_n) correspond to a target $N\%$.

417 *Figure 12. Initial construction deviations corresponding to TPG0 with $p_n=0.50$ with a bottom slope $m=0.04$ for*
 418 *different placement conditions, $\{kp, \Delta/D_n\}$: a) $\{0.20, 0.05\}$, b) $\{0.20, 0.15\}$ and c) $\{0.40, 0.15\}$.*

419 From Figure 11, $\epsilon_{rms}/D_n=0.30$ is associated with a low percentage of significant deviations $N_{\%}\leq 2\%$
 420 corresponding to “Start of Significant Deviations”; thus, acceptable handling conditions $\{kp, \Delta/D_n\}$ may be
 421 those that result in a $\epsilon_{rms}/D_n\leq 0.30$. To this end, Eq. (9) is used to find the corresponding pair of handling
 422 conditions that matches $\epsilon_{rms}\leq 0.30$. As an example, Figure 13 shows the handling conditions for a feasible
 423 construction of Cubipod HLCS ($\epsilon_{rms}/D_n\leq 0.30$ and $N_{\%}\leq 2\%$) with a nominal porosity $p_n=0.500$ and bottom
 424 slope $m=0.04$. Hence, placement velocity (related to a kinetic-to-potential energy ratio) can be selected
 425 according to the dimensionless crane spatial deviation.

426

427 *Figure 13. Handling conditions for feasible construction ($N\% \leq 2\%$ and $\epsilon_{rms}/D_n \leq 0.30$) of Cubipod HLCS ($p_n=0.50$ and*
 428 *$m=0.04$).*

429 **6. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS**

430 The feasibility of constructing 3-layer Cubipod Homogeneous Low Crested Structures (HLCS) is analyzed
 431 using numerical simulations. The Bullet Physics Engine (BPE) is used to carry out a series of numerical
 432 placement tests in different conditions (bottom slope, crane positioning error, etc.). The results of the
 433 numerical experiments were analyzed to understand the influence of the placement grid and placement
 434 conditions during the construction procedure. These results were used to calibrate empirical formulas to
 435 estimate the positioning errors of units from the placement grid and the corresponding initial deviations
 436 depending on the handling characteristics at prototype scale (placement velocity and crane positioning
 437 error).

438 The physics engine BPE was validated with physical experiments by Molines at al. (2021) to estimate the
 439 layer coefficients of 5-layer Cubipod HLCS on a horizontal sea bottom. In this study, the influence of a
 440 design parameter (nominal porosity of HLCS, $0.500 \leq p_n \leq 0.550$), an environmental parameter (bottom
 441 slope, m) and parameters (kp and Δ/D_n) related to unit handling with cranes (placement velocity and GPS-
 442 positioning error) is analyzed to estimate the placement grid shape once constructed. The goal was to predict
 443 the initial construction deviations caused during construction based on the unit handling characteristics.

444 In all, 3,000 numerical tests were conducted for different initial grids TPG0. The range of parameters in the
 445 test matrix was $0.50 \leq p_n$ (nominal porosity) ≤ 0.55 , $0.00 \leq m$ (bottom slope) ≤ 0.06 , $0.005 \leq kp$ (kinetic-to-
 446 potential energy ratio) ≤ 0.080 and $0.00 \leq \Delta/D_n$ (dimensionless crane spatial deviation) ≤ 0.20 . The relatively
 447 low time and computational cost to carry out thousands of numerical tests, involving hundreds of Cubipod
 448 units in realistic construction experiments, make the proposed methodology a relatively simple tool to
 449 optimize construction procedures of HLCS and other maritime structures constructed by gravity. Similar
 450 physical small-scale tests would require a huge investment in time, cost and trained personal.

451 The main conclusions referring to the construction of Cubipod HLCS are as follows:

- 452 1) The Bullet Physics Engine (BPE), which applies Newton's laws of motion to rigid bodies, has
 453 been successfully used with the free open-software Blender (2019) to generate realistic simulations
 454 of the construction procedure of Cubipod HLCS.
 455 2) This numerical model is cost efficient for this task; in this study, thousands of numerical placement
 456 tests involving hundreds of Cubipod units required only 20 weeks with a personal computer (i5
 457 processor).
 458 3) To properly simulate the vertical prototype velocity of Cubipod units during placement, Eq. (6)
 459 can be used to calculate the appropriate size of the units in the numerical model to maintain the
 460 ratio between kinetic and potential energy at the prototype scale.

- 461 4) The numerical model for this study, calibrated with physical experiments to estimate layer
462 coefficients on horizontal bottom, has been found to be very useful to carry out realistic placement
463 tests of Cubipod HLCS with different bottom slopes and prototype crane handling requirements.
464 5) An expansion of the original placement grid, TPG0, was observed; the lower the nominal porosity
465 and higher placement velocity, the higher the grid expansion.
466 6) Gaussian positioning errors, ε_x and ε_y , were observed in the numerical experiments; the higher the
467 placement velocity and bottom slope, the higher the ε_x and ε_y , respectively.
468 7) The final positioning error estimated by Eq. (9) was Rayleigh distributed and the dimensionless
469 root mean squared error (ε_{rms}/D_n) was a function of nominal porosity (p_n) bottom slope (m), kinetic-
470 to-potential energy ratio, (kp) and dimensionless crane spatial deviation (Δ/D_n).
471 8) The numerically-calculated dimensionless root mean squared error (ε_{rms}/D_n) was highly related to
472 the quantitative indicator $N\%$, defined as the percentage of units significantly deviated, $\varepsilon/D_n \geq 1$,
473 from theoretical placement grid.
474 9) Since the construction procedure tends to expand and displace slightly the initial placement grid
475 (see Figure 7 and Figure 8), this information from numerical experiments can be used to improve
476 placement grids of Cubipod HLCS to minimize their initial deviations.
477 10) Handling conditions (kp and Δ/D_n) for the feasible construction of Cubipod HLCS can be obtained
478 for any given placement grid and bottom slope (p_n and m) using Eq. (9).

479 This study focuses on Cubipod HLCS placed on sea bottoms with constant slope. The methodology should
480 be tested for rough bottoms, as well as to optimize placement grids of rocks or other armor units of
481 conventional mound breakwaters. In this case, friction should be calibrated or adjusted depending on
482 material properties.

483 ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

484 This study was funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and “ERDF A way of making Europe”
485 under grants HOLOBREAK (RTI2018-101073-B-I00), REMOBE (PID2021-126475OB-I00) and
486 HOLOBRACE (PID2021-128035OA-I00). The first author is grateful for the *financial support* of
487 MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and “ERDF A way of making Europe” under grant PRE2019-089542.
488 The second author is funded through the Juan de la Cierva 2020 program (FJC2020-044778-I) by “*Unión*
489 *Europea – NextGenerationEU en el marco del Plan de Recuperación, Transformación y Resiliencia de*
490 *España*”, Spanish Ministry of Science and Innovation. The manuscript was revised by Debra Westall
491 (Universitat Politècnica de València, Spain).

492 NOMENCLATURE

493	a	Placement grid spacing along the Y-axis (perpendicular to the trunk)
494	ad	Angular damping
495	b	Placement grid spacing along the X-axis (parallel to the trunk)
496	CM	Collision Margin
497	D_n	Nominal diameter or equivalent cube size of the Cubipod unit
498	$D_{n,n}$	Nominal diameter of the numerical Cubipod
499	$D_{n,p}$	Nominal diameter of the prototype Cubipod
500	e	Bounciness (restitution coefficient)
501	FD	Falling Distance
502	i	Column index to locate Cubipods on the placement grid
503	j	Row index to locate Cubipods on the placement grid
504	k	Layer index to locate Cubipods on the placement grid
505	kp	Kinetic-to-potential energy ratio
506	k_Δ	Layer thickness coefficient

507	ld	Linear damping
508	p_n	Nominal porosity
509	p_v	Void porosity
510	RPG	Rectangular Placement Grid
511	TPG	Triangular Placement Grid
512	TPG0	Initial Triangular Placement Grid
513	v	Placement velocity
514	v_n	Placement velocity of the numerical Cubipod
515	v_p	Placement velocity of the prototype Cubipod
516	γ	Dimensionless placement error
517	Δ/D_n	Dimensionless crane spatial deviation
518	m	Bottom seafloor slope
519	ε	Positioning error
520	ε_{rms}/D_n	Dimensionless root mean squared of the positioning error
521	ε_x	Projected X-positioning error
522	ε_y	Projected Y-positioning error
523	μ	Friction
524	$\rho, \dot{\rho}, \ddot{\rho}$	Linear position, velocity and acceleration
525	$\theta, \dot{\theta}, \ddot{\theta}$	Angular position, velocity and acceleration
526	φ	Dimensionless packing density

527 REFERENCES

- 528 Airoidi, L., Abbiati, M., Beck, M. W., Hawkins, S. J., Jonsson, P. R., Martin, D., Moschella, P. S., Sundelöf,
529 A., Thompson, R. C., & Åberg, P. (2005). An ecological perspective on the deployment and design
530 of low-crested and other hard coastal defence structures. *Coastal Engineering*, 52(10–11), 1073–
531 1087. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2005.09.007>
- 532 Anastasaki, E., Latham, J. P., & Xiang, J. (2015). Numerical modelling of armour layers with reference to
533 Core-Loc units and their placement acceptance criteria. *Ocean Engineering*, 104, 204–218.
534 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.oceaneng.2015.05.010>
- 535 Blender. (2021). *Blender 2.91 Reference Manual*. Accessed October 2022.
536 https://doi.org/https://docs.blender.org/manual/en/2.91/getting_started/index.html
- 537 Boeing, A., & Bräunl, T. (2007). Evaluation of real-time physics simulation systems. *Proceedings -*
538 *GRAPHITE 2007, 5th International Conference on Computer Graphics and Interactive Techniques*
539 *in Australasia and Southeast Asia*, 281–288. <https://doi.org/10.1145/1321261.1321312>
- 540 Centi, R. (2020). *Placement of homogeneous artificial mound breakwaters using a game engine*. University
541 of L’Aquila.
- 542 CIRIA; CUR; CETMEF. (2007). *The Rock Manual. The use of rock in hydraulic engineering. 2nd Edition*.
543 CIRIA, London.
- 544 Cooper, A. K., Greben, J. M., De Villiers, R., Greben, J. M., Van Den Bergh, F., & Gledhill, I. (2010).
545 Simulating the Rubble Mound Underlying Armour. *Seventh South African Conference on*
546 *Computational and Applied Mechanics (SACAM10)*, Pretoria (South Africa). 10-13 January.
547 <https://doi.org/http://hdl.handle.net/10204/5689>

- 548 Cooper, A. K., Greben, J. M., van Den Bergh, F., Gledhill, I., Cannoo, B., Steyn, W., & De Villiers, R.
549 (2008). Preliminary Physics-Engine Model of Dolosse Interacting With One Another. *Sixth South*
550 *African Conference on Computational and Applied Mechanics (SACAM08)*, Pretoria (South Africa).
551 26-28 March. <https://doi.org/http://hdl.handle.net/10204/2386>
- 552 Coumans, E. (2015). *Bullet 2.83 Physics SDK Manual*. Accessed in July 2023.
553 <https://doi.org/http://bulletphysics.org>
- 554 De Keyser, K., & Jacobs, E. (2020). *A literature review on low-crested and submerged structures*. MSc
555 Thesis. Ghent University. <http://lib.ugent.be/catalog/rug01:002945666>
- 556 Erez, T., Tassa, Y., & Todorov, E. (2015). Simulation Tools for Model-Based Robotics : Comparison of
557 Bullet, Havok, MuJoCo, ODE and PhysX. *IEEE International Conference on Robotics and*
558 *Automation (ICRA)*, Seattle, WA, (USA). 26-30 May. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICRA.2015.7139807>
- 559 Greben, J. M., Gledhill, I., Cooper, A. K., & De Villiers, R. (2010). Characterization and properties of
560 breakwater structures modelled by a physics engine. *7th South African Conference on Computational*
561 *and Applied Mechanics, SACAM 2010*, Pretoria (South Africa). 26-28 March.
562 <https://doi.org/http://hdl.handle.net/10204/4978>
- 563 Latham, J. P., Anastasaki, E., & Xiang, J. (2013). New modelling and analysis methods for concrete armour
564 unit systems using FEMDEM. *Coastal Engineering*, 77, 151–166.
565 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2013.03.001>
- 566 Latham, J. P., Munjiza, A., Mindel, J., Xiang, J., Guises, R., Garcia, X., Pain, C., Gorman, G., & Piggott,
567 M. (2008). Modelling of massive particulates for breakwater engineering using coupled FEMDEM
568 and CFD. *Particuology*, 6(6), 572–583. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.partic.2008.07.010>
- 569 Medina, J. R., & Gómez-Martín, M. E. (2016). *Cubipod Manual 2016*. Editorial UPV.
570 <https://doi.org/https://riunet.upv.es/handle/10251/72310?show=full>
- 571 Medina, J. R., Gómez-Martín, M. E., & Corredor, A. (2011). Influence of Armor Unit Placement on Armor
572 Porosity and Hydraulic Stability. *Coastal Engineering Proceedings*, 1(32), 41.
573 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.9753/icce.v32.structures.41>
- 574 Medina, J. R., Gomez-Martin, M. E., Mares-Nasarre, P., Escudero, M., Oderiz, I., Mendoza, E., & Silva,
575 R. (2020). Homogeneous Low-Crested Structures for Beach Protection in Coral Reef Areas. *Coastal*
576 *Engineering Proceedings*, 36v, 59. <https://doi.org/10.9753/icce.v36v.papers.59>
- 577 Medina, J. R., Gómez-Martín, M. E., Mares-Nasarre, P., Oderiz, I., Mendoza, E., & Silva, R. (2019).
578 Hydraulic performance of homogeneous low-crested structures. *Proc. of the Coastal Structures*
579 *Conference 2019*, Bundesanstalt für Wasserbau (BAW), Karlsruhe (GE).
580 https://doi.org/10.18451/978-3-939230-64-9_007
- 581 Medina, J. R., Gómez-Martín, M. E., Molines, J., Mares-Nasarre, P., Escudero, M., Odériz, I., Mendoza,
582 E., & Silva, R. (2022). HOLOBREAK: Homogeneous low-crested structures to protect beaches and
583 regenerate coral reefs. *Proceedings of the 39th IAHR World Congress*, Granada (Spain). 19-24 June.
584 <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.3850/IAHR-39WC252171192022755>
- 585 Millington, I. (2007). Game Physics Engine Development. In *Game Physics Engine Development*. Elsevier
586 Inc. <https://doi.org/10.1016/b978-0-12-369471-3.50001-0>
- 587 Molines, J., Centi, R., Di Risio, M., & Medina, J. R. (2021). Estimation of layer coefficients of cubipod
588 homogeneous low-crested structures using physical and numerical model placement tests. *Coastal*
589 *Engineering*, 168(March). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2021.103901>
- 590 Odériz, I., Mendoza, E., Silva, R., & Medina, J. R. (2018). Stability and Hydraulic performance of a
591 Homogeneous Cubipod Low-crested Mound Breakwater. *7th International Conference on the*
592 *Application of Physical Modelling in Coastal and Port Engineering and Science (CoastLab18)*,
593 Santander (Spain). 22-26 May.
594 [https://doi.org/https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328343836_Stability_and_hydraulic_perfo](https://doi.org/https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328343836_Stability_and_hydraulic_performance_of_a_homogeneous_cubipod_low-crested_mound_breakwater)
595 [rmance_of_a_homogeneous_cubipod_low-crested_mound_breakwater](https://doi.org/https://www.researchgate.net/publication/328343836_Stability_and_hydraulic_performance_of_a_homogeneous_cubipod_low-crested_mound_breakwater)
- 596 Pardo, V., Herrera, M. P., Molines, J., & Medina, J. R. (2014). Placement Test, Porosity, and Randomness
597 of Cube and Cubipod Armor Layers. *Journal of Waterway, Port, Coastal, and Ocean Engineering*,

- 598 140(5), 04014017. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)ww.1943-5460.0000245](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)ww.1943-5460.0000245)
- 599 Schoonees, T., Gijón Mancheño, A., Scheres, B., Bouma, T. J., Silva, R., Schlurmann, T., & Schüttrumpf,
600 H. (2019). Hard Structures for Coastal Protection, Towards Greener Designs. *Estuaries and Coasts*,
601 42(7), 1709–1729. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12237-019-00551-z>
- 602 Sherrard, T. R. W., Hawkins, S. J., Barfield, P., Kitou, M., Bray, S., & Osborne, P. E. (2016). Hidden
603 biodiversity in cryptic habitats provided by porous coastal defence structures. *Coastal Engineering*,
604 118, 12–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coastaleng.2016.08.005>
- 605 Silva, R., Lithgow, D., Esteves, L. S., Martínez, M. L., Moreno-Casasola, P., Martell, R., Pereira, P.,
606 Mendoza, E., Campos-Cascaredo, A., Grez, P. W., Osorio, A. F., Osorio-Cano, J. D., & Rivillas, G.
607 D. (2017). Coastal risk mitigation by green infrastructure in Latin America. *Proceedings of the*
608 *Institution of Civil Engineers: Maritime Engineering*, 170(2), 39–54.
609 <https://doi.org/10.1680/jmaen.2016.13>
- 610 USACE. (1984). *Shore Protection Manual*. Dept. of the Army, Waterways Experiment Station, Corps of
611 Engineers, Coastal Engineering Research Center.
612 <https://doi.org/https://usace.contentdm.oclc.org/digital/collection/p16021coll11/id/1933>
- 613 Xiang, J., Munjiza, A., & Latham, J. P. (2009). Finite strain, finite rotation quadratic tetrahedral element
614 for the combined finite–discrete element method. *International Journal For Numerical Methods in*
615 *Engineering*, 79, 946–978. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1002/nme.2599>